

ISic3600

I.Sicily inscription 3600

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrillae

Place of origin (modern)

Chiaromonte Gulfi

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Chiaramonte Gulfi, Santuario della Beata Maria Vergine di Gulfi (also santuario di Santa Maria la Vetere)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645676

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 57.0886

Rizzone, V.G. 2009. Iscrizioni tardoantiche da Mineo (CT). *Epigraphica*. 71: 426-437. At 431 n.25

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3600. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388799>